

2024

Promoting and sustaining the transition of refugee students to higher education

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Co-funded by the Erasmus+ Programme of the European Union

This project has been funded with the support of the **Erasmus+ programme** of the European Union

Deliverable Factsheet

Project Number:	2022-1-FR01-KA220-HED-000087334
Project Acronym:	AGILE
Project Title:	Higher education resilience in refugee crises: forging social inclusion through capacity building, civic engagement and skills recognition.
Document Title:	Promoting and sustaining the transition of refugee students to higher education
Work package:	WP3
Submission Date:	14/10/2024
Graphic designer	Ioanna Tsakarelou, Web2Learn
Authors(s):	Sílvia Melo-Pfeifer, Lisa Marie Brinkmann and Franziska Gerwers
External reviewer(s):	Prof. Dr. Vasilía Kourtis-Kazoullis, University of the Aegean, Rhodes, Greece
Version Status	V04
Approved by:	All Partners
Abstract:	In this document, we shed light on the factors impeding refugee students to enrol in Higher Education (HE) programmes and pursue their learning and professional journey once they have settled in the host country. We summarise the main results obtained during the development of the AGILE project around the theme of 'transitions', including the (multimodal) voices of HE institutions and the refugee students who study there. We end with perspectives on good practices to facilitate the transition of refugee students from host institutions and structures to higher education.
Keyword list:	Higher education resilience, transitions, whole university approach.
Copyright	Creative Commons License 4.0 International
Dissemination Level	Public
Please cite as	Melo-Pfeifer, S., Brinkmann, L.M., & Gerwers, F. (2023) <i>Promoting and sustaining the transition of refugee students to higher education</i> . AGILE consortium. URL: https://agileproject-erasmus.eu/ (section « Results »). Doi : 10.25592/uhhfdm.16520

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Polish Rectors Foundation (PRF)

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Revision History

Version	Date	Revised by	Reason
V0.2	01.10.2024	Lisa Marie Brinkmann and Franziska Gerwers	Internal review
V0.3	17.10.2024	Iryna Degtyarova, Léa Meunier, Anthippi Potolia, Katerina Zourou	Internal review by partners
v0.4	08.11.2024	Prof. Dr. Vasilias Kourtis-Kazoullis, University of the Aegean, Rhodes, Greece	External review

Statement of originality:

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

Disclaimer:

This project has been funded with support from the European Commission. This deliverable reflects the views only of the author, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

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List of Abbreviations

The following table presents the acronyms used in the deliverable in alphabetical order.

Abbreviations	Description
EU	European Union
HE	Higher Education
HEI	Higher Education Institution

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Executive Summary

In this document, we shed light on the factors impeding refugee students enrolling in Higher Education (HE) programs and pursue their learning and professional journey once they have settled in the host country. We summarize the main results obtained during the development of the AGILE project around the theme of 'transitions', including the (multimodal) voices of HE institutions and the refugee students who study there. We end with perspectives on good practices to facilitate the transition of refugee students from host institutions and structures to higher education.

The AGILE project

This publication is a result of the EU-funded AGILE project ("Higher education resilience in refugee crises: forging social inclusion through capacity building, civic engagement and skills recognition", <http://www.agileproject-erasmus.eu/>), whose aim is to increase resilience of HE systems to address the ongoing needs of refugees through social participation and skills recognition. The AGILE project aims to enrich HE curricula by proposing new pedagogical designs that encourage grassroots and digitally-enhanced actions in both formal and informal learning environments.

The project is coordinated by the University Paris 8. The consortium is made up of six universities (University Paris 8, Bordeaux Montaigne University, University of Hamburg, University of Ljubljana, Lviv Polytechnic National University, Kaunas University of Technology), one think-tank (Polish Rectors Foundation) and one business partner (Web2Learn) who specialises in open recognition systems and social learning.

1. Introduction

1. Introduction

As stated by Unangst (2019), “the refugee influx in the European context has challenged national systems and individual higher education institutions to develop and iterate solutions for prospective and, increasingly, enrolled university students” (2019, p. 144). Nevertheless, even if literature is already available about support mechanisms at the higher educational level (Ashour, 2022; Berg, 2019; Friedrich, Ruano & Melo-Pfeifer, 2021; Schröder, et al, 2022; Unangst & Streitwieser, 2018), it tends to focus on specific hosting countries or/and specific refugee populations. Additionally, it tends to be based on data collected from people involved in the institutions (university and counselling staff, for example) and less from (potential) beneficiaries of these mechanisms (the refugee students themselves) (see Grüttner et al, 2018, for an exception). In this document, we provide an overview of support mechanisms and good practices supporting transitions from refugee students in different AGILE partner countries and two non-EU countries (Brazil and Turkey), presenting both institutional voices and the voices of refugee students.

The issue of the particularities of refugee students’ profiles has been discussed in a controversial way, raising questions about the (lack of) self-identification and top-down ascribed identities. Berg (2018), for example, claims that “it can be assumed that, to some extent, refugees face similar difficulties as all international students, amplified by and in addition to hindrances arising from their specific situation” (pp. 221-222). Other research on international students in HE has pinpointed the differences between voluntarily displaced students making a period abroad (such as those in Erasmus study programs), migrant students, and refugee students, highlighting the different aims, challenges, future perspectives, and legal and residence obligations these three different groups might have as well as the different institutional structures and ideologies accommodating them (Unangst, 2025; see also Unangst & de Wit, 2021). Unangst makes it clear that institutions might be differently equipped to financially support the differentiation of all international students, hindering “equity across admission, support, curricula, and other policy and practice domains” (2025, p. 7). This document does not aspire to compare support mechanisms designed to welcome international students in the three categories above but focuses on support mechanisms to welcome refugee students in HE. As we will see, such support mechanisms might be directed to facilitate transitions from refugee-welcoming structures to HE.

In this academic context, there is a notable shortage of research, particularly concerning the integration, presence, and educational journey of refugee students (see Arar et al. 2019; Ramsay and Baker 2019; Ruano 2019). Both in the past and currently, refugees have had very limited opportunities to access HE, despite the fact that “many refugees and asylum seekers have high educational aspirations” (2018, p. 219). One of the challenges to accessing HE might well be the difficulties of coping with institutional and other life-related transitions in the life of refugee students: socio-economical, linguistic and cultural, educational, among others. In an analysis by Ruano and Melo-Pfeifer (2023), the authors state that

According to a report from the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR 2016; 2020), 'despite their potential, young refugees are greatly disadvantaged in accessing university education as well as technical and vocational training' (2016). This would explain why only 1% of refugee students are enrolled in higher education, compared to 34% youth around the world (idem; also UNESCO 2019). According to the same report, getting to university and obtaining a certified diploma is even more difficult for girls than it is for boys (p. 136).

This statement underscores the strong disparity between refugee students and their non-refugee peers, highlighting how refugee students (and particularly girls; see also Unangst, 2019, on the under-representation of women among refugee students) are at a severe disadvantage when it comes to educational opportunities, even though many of them have the potential to succeed if given the chance. These disadvantages might include financial constraints, lack of documentation, language barriers, discrimination, and unstable living and family conditions at arrival (separated families, for example), all of which make it difficult for refugees to pursue further education or technical skills and education. In this document we analyse such disadvantages in light of the concept of "transition" and we propose some ideas to facilitate transitions in refugee students' lives, focusing on transitions from welcoming structures to the Higher Education Institutions (HEIs).

The document is divided into four main parts:

- "On the definition of 'transition' from a human developmental perspective", where we discuss the concept of transition and reflect on how transitions (mainly to higher education) might be even more difficult for refugee than for regular students;
- "Which transitions are salient from the refugee students' perspectives? Insights from visual linguistic autobiographies", where we analyse visual productions by refugee students, underscoring the transitions depicted in their autobiographies;
- "Why are transitions problematic? Lessons from the AGILE questionnaire", in which we recall the results of the AGILE survey among refugee students, highlighting the difficulties attached to transitions to HE;
- "How can universities facilitate transitions to higher education? Good practices in AGILE institutions and beyond", where the results with HE stakeholders from the AGILE roundtables will be reanalysed in light of transitions;

The document, which is highly illustrated by voices from the field, i.e. both the students and the HEIs, is expected to give practitioners and stakeholders ideas on how to conciliate efforts to reduce challenges in transitions.

2. On the definition of “transition” from a human developmental perspective

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To understand the concept of transition, we could say that it derives from the Latin *transitionem* (nominative *transitio*) meaning “a going across or over” and highlighting a process rather than a product, referring to changes that might induce tensions and conflicts (as recent political events around “transition of power” have shown (Lingard de la Vega et al., 2023, p. 423).

Based on Bronfenbrenner’s (1979) ecological theory, individuals go through multiple “ecological transitions” during their lifetimes, transitions that occur “whenever a person’s position within their ecological environment is altered due to a change in role, setting, or both” (Bronfenbrenner, 1979, p. 26). Examples regarding such transitions related to life changes can be changes in the school environment, the birth of a child, getting married, immigration, or exile. From here, we can conclude that transition is usually associated with tensions and/or uncertainties.

In exile and refugee contexts, individuals undergo significant transitions in their (linguistic) lives, impacting their identities and linguistic repertoires, which adapt in dynamic and unpredictable ways. Exile is a key moment of transition in one’s (linguistic) biography, influencing both personal development and transformation. In transitional experiences, an individual is not a “blank slate upon which the environment imposes itself, but rather a growing and dynamic entity that gradually integrates into and reshapes the environment in which they reside” (Bronfenbrenner, 1979, p. 21), demonstrating agency. Following Anderson et al. (2004, p. 9), Singh et al. (2023, p. 11) explain that

refugees experience two major transitions that can have a profound impact on their lives: “First, the flight from their home country, which in some cases is prolonged and characterized by extreme deprivation and traumatic experiences; and second, their arrival, at a time when their personal resources are low, in a host country which often differs radically from that to which they are accustomed” [Anderson, 2004, p. 9]. However, being a refugee means being in a constant move between not just geographical, but also cultural, institutional and/or psychological places and spaces.

More specifically, when talking about transitions in educational systems or across educational systems, transitions and the success of transitions might not be only dependent upon students’ abilities, but rather on institutional characteristics. Lingard de la Vega et al. (2023) claim that transitions “might not occur automatically and be dependent on the assessment of students’ performances (in some cases even being connected to institutional discrimination, Gomolla & Radtke, 2009) or on the availability of adequate curricular offers, influencing continuation or disruption in students’ school paths” (p. 423). Having said this, systemic biases (Unangst, 2025) - whether based on race, gender, socio-economic status, or other factors - can play a role in determining who gets to advance in their education and the availability of appropriate curricular programs, educational resources, and institutional

structures also influence whether students can continue their studies. Bacakova also claims that transitions are even more challenging for refugees with disabilities (2023), adding more obstacles to the vulnerabilities of this particular student population.

These considerations about conditional transitions are also relevant to understand the transition of refugee students from welcoming centres (such as refugee camps or initial settlement schools) to HE. First, just like other students, refugee students' progression from welcoming centres to HE is not automatic. They must often meet specific academic or performance criteria, which may be challenging due to factors like language barriers, gaps in education, disabilities, or the trauma they have experienced. Second, challenges in transition might include policies, practices, or attitudes within schools and universities that particularly disadvantage refugee students, such as difficulties in getting previous educational qualifications recognized, biased or over-bureaucratized admissions processes, or lack of adequate support for language acquisition and housing. Third, a lack of targeted programs (such as language support, academic preparation, or integration assistance) also might lead to disruption in transitions or high drop-out rates among refugee students. In any case, as stated by Naidoo et al., "even though traditional institutional environments may constrain transition for refugee background students, transition is a process, not an outcome" (2018, p. 157). The same authors state that

Successful transition and participation in new educational contexts for refugee background students' needs to be reconceptualised by universities as a holistic process that builds an enabling learning culture. Such a culture rejects a deficit approach to learning and is inextricably linked to the development of positive interpersonal relationships with peers, teachers, support staff and the wider community combined with the ability to navigate the higher education system (2018, p. 157).

In the next sections, we will analyse which transitions are considered salient from the refugee students' perspectives, how they might be considered problematic, and how universities can facilitate transitions more systematically and holistically. As a whole, we consider that

the role of refugee education is to support the transformation of life course *ruptures* into transitions between past and future, to shed light on *passages* towards membership in diverse communities, and to mediate the *re-orientation* of educational policy and practices having in mind the evolving identities of refugees in a changing world. (Singh et al, 2023, p. 10, italics by the authors).

3. Which transitions are salient from the refugee students' perspectives? Insights from visual linguistic autobiographies

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In this section, we report on the results obtained through an arts-based approach workshop with refugee students participating at a summer school organized by the AGILE project (Potolia et al., 2024). In these workshops, students were instructed to draw their language biography (see Kalaja & Melo-Pfeifer, 2024; Melo-Pfeifer, 2023 on this methodology), to share them with colleagues (on a voluntary basis), and to give feedback to the other students through collages of colorful post-its with a message in a language of their choice.

One of the results is that fleeing from war scenarios was visualized as a moment of transition in participants' biographies, with consequences at linguistic and career levels (Image 1). More specifically, we could observe that linguistic transitions are associated with geographical and cross-border transitions, linked to different nation-states.

Image 1. Language biography by a Ukrainian refugee student based in Germany.

Such transitions were lived with desires to lose parts of their plurilingual identity (in the case that language was also the language of the invader and reason for exile; image 2) and to acquire other languages, mainly for instrumental learning purposes.

Image 2. Language biography by a Ukrainian refugee student based in Poland.

Nevertheless, despite the disruption in the linguistic biographies, with the need to leave Ukraine (and the language signalled with a red heart), the student in image 2 shows resilience in the new “current home” (a word that is further illustrated by a happy smile). The text accompanying this drawing is rich in possessive pronouns (“my current home”, “my school”, “my second school”, “my university”), showing agency in different transitional moments.

Image 3. Language biography by an Iranian refugee student in France.

This third drawing shows a linguistic and biographic path attached to several forced displacements, first to Turkey and subsequently to France. As in the previous drawings, the author represents languages that were learned in the school curriculum in the home country (English) and languages that were formally learned or informally acquired due to forced displacement (in this case, Turkish and French).

What seems to be common in these linguistic biographies that portray transitions between countries and languages is the lack of importance given to foreign languages previously acquired in the country of origin and the concentration on the proficiency of the majority language of the host country(ies). Of course, this could be considered a limitation of the methodology itself, which is centred on linguistic experiences, but what seems interesting is that the students draw transition periods associated with linguistic transitions which, with each new biographical moment, seem to bring new cracks and crashes in the subjects' experiences. Although this methodology (drawing a linguistic biography) may not be the most suitable for studying biographical transitions in their complexity, focusing only on the linguistic facet, it illustrates how (successive) transitions in the lives of refugee university students are associated with successive linguistic learning and how previously acquired languages become useless in new contexts due to a hyper-entrenchment in the majority language of the host countries. Thus, the "intersection of different 'displacements'" (Unangst & de Wit, 2021) is also about the intersection of different language competences, despite the fact that students tend to visualize linear paths.

4. Why are transitions problematic? Lessons from the AGILE questionnaire with refugee students

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155 refugee students from France, Poland, Germany, Slovenia, Lithuania, Italy, and Ukraine (host countries) answered the online survey during the last trimester of 2023, but the majority of respondents were from France and Poland (see Lawrence, 2024). This survey was designed to listen to students' voices, a pressing issue named by Unganst and de Wit (2021), when they call to "understanding from the perspective of displaced learners how support structures function to promote or inhibit higher education access and success" (2021, p. 8).

The answers to our survey provided a perspective that most of the refugee students inquired had already studied at a HEI in their home country and were therefore trying to re-enter academia (image 4).

Image 4. Did you already study at a university in your home country? (65% Yes; 35% No)

These answers allow us to admit that students entering HE for the first time or trying to re-enter HE might have different transitional challenges. Indeed, students trying to re-enter academia might need to cope with changes in the academic culture, from expectations about participation and teaching-learning styles to grading; all of which might differ from what they experienced before. These challenges are coupled with linguistic issues, which are common to students entering HE for the first time. Indeed, in addition to academic adjustments, refugee students often face linguistic challenges, which are common to both first-time entrants and returning students. Language barriers may make it difficult for them to fully engage in coursework, participate in discussions, or grasp nuanced academic content, all of which can hinder their ability to succeed and lead to drop-out rates. In these cases, to facilitate transition to a new academic culture, refugee students might need to be informed about the new academic setting and how they could better accommodate to it.

Among those refugee students who already studied in their home countries, 28% had to change their subject. The motives for changing courses, according to the participants, stem from a variety of factors, including shifting career prospects, evolving personal priorities or interests, the availability or accessibility of new or different subjects, and language considerations. Students may choose to switch courses as they reassess their future career

paths, find new academic interests, or discover subjects that were previously unavailable. Additionally, the language of instruction can play a significant role, as students may opt for courses taught in a language they are more comfortable with or need for their future goals. To address the challenges that arise from students changing courses due to shifting career prospects, evolving interests, new subject availability, or language barriers, HEIs could implement support mechanisms that go beyond language barriers. These mechanisms could focus on academic counselling and possibilities of academic continuity, such as attention to other issues than language skills. This would allow for smoother transitions through the creation of academic environments where students can change their academic trajectory without unnecessary setbacks or feeling that all they need to succeed in academic skills. One student referred to the difficulties in transitioning from one career path to another in these terms: "The problem of development in another speciality in which I am not very good"¹. This sentence makes it clear that students might be forced to change their specialty, with an impact on how they see their professional self (as "not as good as if...").

Another burden for students who already studied in their home countries is the issue of diploma recognition: some students reveal that their diplomas were accepted, but others were just recognized after completion of further requirements, while in some cases previous diplomas were not accepted/recognized at all.

Despite not all students being informed about support mechanisms offered by the universities they are enrolled in (3% of the students declared that their institutions offered no support at all), the fact that only 64% of the participants declared having used them in the past is more revealing. This data suggests a potential communication gap between universities and their students regarding available services. Additionally, even when support mechanisms are available, a substantial portion of students either choose not to use them, are unaware of their relevance, or may face barriers to accessing them. This means that the existence of support mechanisms does not necessarily translate into their use, which could point to issues related to outreach, accessibility, or perceived effectiveness of the services offered. Among the most used support services are language courses (96%), financial support (82%), administrative help (63%), academic counselling (57%), additional courses and tutoring (57%), and psychological counselling (55%). The data suggests that refugee students in HE have distinct and pressing needs across various aspects of their academic and personal lives. One student declared that refugee students have these pressing needs:

Helping with legal advice for refugee students and giving them lot of support by helping with flat or job search, research programs. Besides that, it is good to know that you can ask your tutor from administrative department when you have any issues. Exchange between hosting and hosted students also lets you being integrated in new society. (Refugee student in Germany)

It should be noted that the fact that 96% of the students are taking language classes (for example, German classes in Germany or French classes in France) might have a double interpretation: first, the language is paramount to follow studies in the host country, meaning that ideologies of internationalization and English Medium of Instruction (known as EMI) are not widespread; second, it might be indicative of ideologies putting the burden of academic success in refugees' linguistic skills only. Such a stance might jeopardize refugee

¹ The quotations are directly transcribed from the open questions of the survey.

students and institutions in their need to see beyond linguistic challenges and engage with other barriers to inclusion and academic success.

In terms of financial support, this data points towards a significant reliance on financial aid. Indeed, refugee students often face financial hardships, making it difficult for them to cover tuition fees, living expenses (such as housing), and other education-related costs. Financial support seems vital for their ability to remain enrolled in universities, even if the initial transition was successful.

Students who were trying to re-enter the academic system in the host country reported “low support from my home university”, implying that successful transitions require a strong inter-institutional collaboration.

Apart from this lack of inter-institutional dialogue, students also reported on cumulative burdens, such as this student when s/he lists the journey of difficulties s/he has been through in transitioning to a new academic environment:

Adapting to a new environment after coming from a war zone and learning a new language as well as going through administrative processes since my class was the first ever international preparatory class in my school (Refugee student in Germany).

To wrap up, the AGILE survey allowed us to uncover the challenges in transition as shown in table 1:

Table 1. Challenges in transition, from the perspective of refugee students.

<p>Academic transition challenges</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Re-entering students face difficulties adjusting to new academic cultures (participation, teaching styles, grading). • Both new and re-entering students encounter linguistic and intercultural barriers, affecting engagement in coursework and academic success. • New students who finished secondary school in the host country might benefit from structures mediating between secondary schools and universities, which are, to time, rather rare (Naidoo et al., 2015 and 2018).
<p>Course changes in the transition to a new academic system</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An important percentage of refugee students had to change their academic subjects due to shifting career prospects, evolving interests, new subject availability, or language barriers. • Course changes may impact students' self-perception, especially when transitioning to unfamiliar fields.
<p>Gaps in (communicating about) support mechanisms</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some students were unaware of support services at their universities. • Only a part of them had used support mechanisms, indicating a communication and accessibility gap. • Some mismatch between support offered and wished.
<p>Heavy reliance on language courses</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High demand for language courses reflects the necessity of proficiency in the host country's language. • Overemphasis on language skills might detract from addressing other critical barriers to academic success and hinder transformative curricular and institutional practices.
<p>Financial challenges</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Many refugee students rely on financial aid to cover tuition, housing, and living expenses, essential for academic persistence.
<p>Lack of inter-institutional collaboration</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some students report low support from their home universities, highlighting the need for stronger collaboration between institutions in home and host countries. • Difficulties in diploma recognition.

5. How can universities facilitate transitions to higher education? Good practices in AGILE institutions and beyond

5. How can universities facilitate transitions to higher education? Good practices in AGILE institutions and beyond

According to the released document “Principles for institutional change and curriculum design to welcome refugee students in Higher Education”, co-authored by Melo-Pfeifer and Gerwers (2023), HEIs can support refugee students before, during, and after their arrival to the institution (image 4), adapting a whole university approach (Image 5):

What does a whole university approach look like?

Image 5. A whole university approach (see Friedrich et al. 2021).

This image shows the need for higher education institutions to create synergies between other institutions, such as associations and NGOs, and to coordinate transition facilitation efforts with other organizations at the macro level (see Lawrence, 2024). At the meso level, institutions might need to rethink their structures, creating diversified support mechanisms for refugee students, instead of amalgamating this particular profile of international students to others such as (Erasmus) exchange students. At the micro level, it is important to implement measures that support refugee students’ engagement with specific courses, content and curriculum.

The empirical data for such a claim resulted from three round tables with stakeholders in HE in Europe, mainly those of the AGILE project, and beyond (Brazil and Turkey).

Image 6. Levels of academic support for refugee students and associated principles (Melo-Pfeifer & Gerwers, 2023, p. 13).

As we concentrate on transitions to HE in this document, we will focus this section on the level “before”, which included 5 out of 10 principles:

- P3. Combine standardized welcoming procedures with more personalized and individual ones
- P4. Develop a holistic approach to refugee students’ integration
- P5. Create structures to facilitate enrolment, permanence, and success
- P6. Train your staff to address the needs of refugee students
- P9. Develop resilient and sustainable welcoming structures

HE representatives who participated in the AGILE round tables highlighted, in relation to P3, the challenges of applying standard enrolment procedures to refugee students, emphasizing the need for institutional flexibility and adjustments. One stakeholder from a Turkish university referred to challenges in detecting specific problems during the enrolment process and to practices that were effectively closing doors to undocumented refugees. They suggested balancing standardized welcoming processes with personalized, case-by-case approaches to create a fair yet inclusive environment. Participants acknowledged that standardizing procedures in admission processes might be dehumanizing, by not addressing particular experiences of candidates. A Slovenian representative recognized that one particular challenge was the recognition of previous education and that the recognition of adults’ education degrees was even more difficult. This would involve streamlining enrolment for consistency and accountability while offering tailored support, such as academic advising, career counselling, and assistance for students with specific needs, like family needs or health issues. In this sense, data from our stakeholders match the needs reported by students in our questionnaire (see section 4 of this document).

Concerning P4, participants in the round tables referred to the need to implement holistic models requiring coordinated efforts across departments, involving task forces with refugee student representation and providing services like language training, legal support, housing, financial aid, and mental health assistance. This stance also shows a strong correspondence with students’ answers (see section 4). Additionally, connecting with civil society to create internship and employment opportunities is essential. Overall, participants stressed the importance of aligning their university policies, services, and culture with external collaborations to ensure refugee students’ success, reduce drop-out rates, and foster institutional development and participation. What was not mentioned, in contrast to the refugee students’ voices (section 4, above), was the need to develop close collaborations with students’ institutions in the home countries.

About P5, “Create structures to facilitate enrolment, permanence, and success”, participants in the round tables agreed on the need to create various structures and support mechanisms to facilitate enrolment, recognize prior education and credentials, and promote academic success while reducing drop-out rates. Among the measures best adapted to meet challenges at the transition level academic advising and support, financial aid office, scholarship and financial support programs, and housing assistance could be emphasized. Despite the overlapping with students’ answers, what should be mentioned is that even when such mechanisms are created and made available, there seems to be a gap in the communication between institutions and the refugee students (see previous section).

Regarding P6, stakeholders stated that training to effectively welcome and support refugee students should focus on promoting intercultural sensitivity and understanding of refugee experiences. They also referred to the need to educate multidisciplinary teams to address refugee students' needs more holistically. This training should encompass several key areas, such as intercultural competence to help educators understand diverse values, languages, religions, communication styles, and academic traditions; trauma-informed care to sensitively address mental health issues and connect students with appropriate resources; and legal training that covers visa status, work permits, documentation challenges, and their evolution in response to geopolitical conflicts. Additionally, the training should include inclusive and anti-discriminatory practices, such as multilingual teaching and assessment methods, as well as conflict resolution strategies. The Brazilian representatives addressed particular intercultural issues related to the increased search for support for a predominantly feminine refugee population and the upsurge of Indigenous populations searching for protection (see also Unangst & Steitwieser, 2018, on "Enabling access for women refugees [as] a key goal", p. 287). The Slovenian representatives also conceded that the majority of applicants for temporary protection were female (66%). Alongside issues of trauma (not only related to war but also to climatic urgencies and gender-based violence in home countries), the Brazilian participants point to the fact that staff at the institutions should be educated to deal with issues of xenophobia, racism and sexism in welcoming structures.

Finally, in relation to P9, which referred to "Develop resilient and sustainable welcoming structures", stakeholders from HE acknowledged that many support structures for refugee students in their institutions are set up reactively during emergencies and are not intended to be permanent. Ideally, sustainable and resilient support systems should be established through long-term strategies, secured funding, and integration into institutional frameworks. Indeed, as shown by Berg, "How far [universities] can support refugees depends on funding, individual engagement and also on previously existing structures" (2018, p. 231). This means that institutional support mechanisms must be anchored in their previous histories and be adaptable to new emergencies, in a movement of constant growth and building on previous experiences. During discussions, university policymakers suggested the need for contacts, and stable financing to better support refugee students. One of the main issues in supporting transition for refugee students, most of the stakeholders agreed upon, is the heavy dependence on engaged but short-term staff, working mostly on a voluntary basis.

6. Synthesis: bringing together institutional and refugee students' voices

6. Synthesis: bringing together institutional and refugee students' voices

The data presented in sections 3 to 5 gives us some ideas about how HEIs could support refugee students' transitions. As put by Friedrich et al. (2021),

Promoting the integration of migrant and refugee students in Higher Education cannot be seen as detached from the broader context; it depends on initiatives facilitating the enrolment in a specific course (...micro level), but it happens in meso and macro contexts, meaning, the University as an environment (meso level) in interaction with the city, the society and the political scenarios (the macro level) (2021, p. 115).

Following the content presented in this document, and disregarding some mismatches between refugee students' and stakeholders' voices, the following ideas for good practices in the implementation of "student support constellations" (Unangst & de Wit, 2021, p. 8) could be implemented (image 7).

Image 7. The specificities of a whole university approach to facilitate transitions.

In this last section, and aligned with the principle that tertiary education should be "equally accessible to all" (United Nations, 1963), we synthesize the measures that could be developed to ensure equity in access to HE. Because we recognize that best practices are not based on one-fits-all solutions but require critical adaptability and constant evaluation of support mechanisms, according to the institution and the society where it operates, the following synthesis should be interpreted as a set of possible points of departure for making transitions to HE softer and less embedded in symbolic violence (table 2).

Table 2. Good practices to support transitions to higher education.

Good practices facilitating transitions	
Streamline administrative processes	Simplifying enrolment and administrative processes: reducing bureaucratic obstacles and providing administrative guidance, including for visa status, documentation, and legal requirements.
Academic transition support	HEIs should offer academic counselling and orientation, namely for students who already initiated their studies in their home country, therefore minimizing disruption to their studies. They could allow credit transfers and flexible pathways such as students re-entering HE or switching academic tracks. This action area could also be fulfilled by providing personalized academic and career advice for students reassessing their future paths, ensuring smooth transitions and more self-confidence in new fields of study.
Language support	The provision of intensive language courses is acknowledged by refugee students and host institutions as paramount for academic success. Beyond offering courses focused on language proficiency in the host country's majority language, institutions could also incorporate bilingual or multilingual options to ease students' transition and ensure that language support is complemented by addressing other academic barriers (e.g., tutoring, writing assistance) to avoid overburdening students with linguistic challenges alone.
Comprehensive support services to address cumulative challenges	HEIs could enhance outreach to ensure students are fully aware of available resources, using multiple communication channels and onboarding sessions. Information and equity in the distribution of such support should be assured.
Financial aid	To ensure access to financial support, HEIs could create flexible financial aid packages tailored to refugee students' needs (tuition fees, housing, living expenses, health and child care, ...). Knowing that refugee students might have documentation challenges, institutions should make the attribution of such packages straightforward and transparent. Nevertheless, it should be noted that "the HEIs support of refugees depends on funding" (Berg, 2018, p. 333).
Inter-institutional collaboration (with	To facilitate diploma and credit recognition, HEIs could collaborate with universities in students' home countries to ensure smoother transitions and recognition of prior learning.

origin countries and national institutions)	Additionally, institutions should engage more with each other, at national and international levels, about their support mechanisms (design, implementation, and assessment of efficacy).
Mental health and psychological support	Refugee students were not voluntarily displaced but went through life-threatening situations. HEIs could therefore offer trauma-informed counselling, sensitive to the trauma and mental health needs of refugee students, considering their past experiences. Counsellors should be made aware that specific groups (women, indigenous people, victims of gender-based violence) might need specific health and psychological support.

To wrap up, this table shows that good practices to support refugee students' transitions to HE are those which offer holistic support, recognizing and addressing the cumulative challenges this specific international population faces, including adjusting to a new academic environment, learning new languages, coping with trauma, and navigating administrative and juridical hurdles. Because the challenges are cumulative, the path to smooth transitions is also multi-sited and intertwined, despite some visible fragmentations in the available services (fragmentation also visible in Ashour, 2022, systematic literature review) across countries and across institutions:

Nationally-specific menus of programs supporting displaced populations span national, state, and local government, the non-profit and religious sectors, etc. and also involve social workers, career civil servants, and both HEI and private counselors, among other actors. Services may include: food banks, transportation services, child care, job boards/advising, mental health services, tutoring in a range from more (1:1) to less (peer group) intensive, emergency funds for unexpected expenses, athletics/recreation programs, and more (Unangst & de Wit, 2021, p. 7).

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Acknowledgements

This collection was produced as part of Work Package 3 of the EU-funded project AGILE: "Higher education resilience in refugee crises: forging social inclusion through capacity building, civic engagement and skills recognition." (www.agileproject-erasmus.eu, Project Number 2022-1-FR01-KA220-HED-000087334). The authors of this study would like to thank all AGILE' partner organisations for their input into the research and resource gathering stage of this project, as well as during the review of the guide.

This project has been funded with support from the European Commission. This deliverable reflects the views only of the author, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

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